

**Digital, autonomous, Intelligent and Synchronous system for
Continuous identification, Optimization and Value Extraction of
Resources from the end-of-use built environment**

DISCOVER

D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

**WP 8 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
(M1 -M18)**

WP Leader: PEDMEDE

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
DC Plan	Dissemination & Communication Plan
DE&C	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
MOOCs	Massive Open Online Courses
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance indicators
EoL	End-of-life

List of figures

Figure 1. The main pillars of the D&C activities	8
Figure 2. D&C Timeline	10
Figure 3. DISCOVER's target groups	12
Figure 4. Alternative versions of the logo	13
Figure 5. Snapshot of the DISCOVER website.....	16
Figure 6. Snapshot of DISCOVER's LinkedIn account	17
Figure 7. Snapshot of DISCOVER's X account	17

List of tables

Table 1. Dissemination & Communication Phases, Objectives, and Tools.....	10
Table 2: DISCOVER's communication channels and tools.....	12
Table 3. DISCOVER Hashtag list.....	18
Table 4. Indicative list of events	20
Table 5. Indicative list of scientific journals.....	21
Table 6. Demo site events.....	22
Table 7. Related EU-funded projects	26
Table 8. DISCOVER's Key Performance Indicators	27

Table of contents

About the DISCOVER project	5
Abstract	6
Introduction.....	7
1. Communication and Dissemination Objectives	8
2. Timeline of D&C Plan.....	9
3. Target Groups.....	11
3.1. Gender Dimension.....	12
4. Communication main channels and tools	12
4.1. Visual identity	13
4.2. EU Visual identity.....	13
4.3. Promotional materials	14
4.4. DISCOVER Project website.....	15
4.5. Social media accounts	16
4.6. Newsletters	18
4.7. Media releases.....	19
5. Dissemination channels and tools.....	19
5.1. Events.....	19
5.2. Scientific publications	20
5.3. Demo site events and MOOCS	21
5.4. DISCOVER Final dissemination event.....	22
6. Clustering Networks and Synergies.....	23
6.1. Roles and responsibilities.....	26
7. Monitoring and evaluation of CD activities.....	27
7.1. Dissemination and Communication monitoring.....	28
Conclusion.....	29
Annexes	30

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About the DISCOVER project

DISCOVER intends to develop an autonomous, synchronous, continuous and intelligent identification and data analysis system for materials and products in existing end-of-life built works. The proposed approach will provide key stakeholders, including academia research performers, along with construction industry representatives, with data-driven insights to make deconstruction more efficient, optimise the use of resources, improve the environmental footprints and enhance the circularity of construction and demolition, unlocking the potential of end-of-life built works, which will become material banks. The expected outcomes include an autonomous robotic platform coupled with continuous identification tools to scan built works and provide synchronous quantitative and qualitative data from different materials, including complex and concealed elements. Artificial intelligence algorithms will allow a rapid analysis of the properties and characteristics of components, and feed the automated scan-to-BIM model creation. The multi-dimensional BIM, including selective demolition processes, labour productivity, and technical planning, will become a Digital Twin of the demolition site optimised by social, economic, and environmental multi-criteria assessments. This approach will highly contribute to increase significantly the supply of traceable and sustainable construction materials and products to enhance their wider market acceptance, following the waste hierarchy. The social impacts of digital transformation in the construction sector will be considered, and new professional development tools for the relevant stakeholders will be proposed. The system will be tested in four different real demolition sites (Spain, Portugal, Poland and Belgium), offering a complete range of built work typologies and wide geographical coverage to demonstrate the replicability potential of DISCOVER, increasing the project dissemination capacity and awareness among the construction sector.

Abstract

The present document constitutes Deliverable D8.1 “Dissemination & Communication Plan” (DC Plan) in the framework of Work Package 8 “Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication”, which is a comprehensive document detailing the tools, channels and activities that will be utilized throughout the project to ensure effective and consistent representation of the DISCOVER Project, as well as its activities and outcomes, for successful dissemination of results.

This DC Plan aims to lay out the strategy to be followed by project partners to communicate the project’s results to the audience, which includes key stakeholders (end-users, construction and deconstruction companies, the scientific community, industry stakeholders), the media, and the general public. This report summarizes the strategy of the consortium to (1) raise awareness of the project and its achievements, (2) maximize the impact of the project and effectively engage with a diverse range of target groups, and (3) ensure the effectiveness and sustainability of the project impact.

The document details the communication and dissemination channels that the project will employ, as well as specific tools and activities such as visual identity, communication materials, scientific publications, participation in events and other actions. Moreover, a basic toolbox of templates for the DISCOVER consortium partners has been provided.

In particular, the document is structured as follows:

Chapter 1: An introduction to the DISCOVER DC Plan and its goals;

Chapter 2: The overview of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) objectives;

Chapter 3: The timeline of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan throughout the duration of the project;

Chapter 4: The target audience of the DISCOVER project;

Chapter 5: The tools and channels used to communicate the project’s activities and results to the identified stakeholders;

Chapter 6: The tools and channels used to disseminate the project’s activities and results to the identified stakeholders;

Chapter 7: The importance of establishing synergies with other relevant projects and networks throughout the duration of the project.

Chapter 8: The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) utilized to assess the dissemination efforts and enable the project consortium to implement effective strategies to enhance the project's impact; description of the process of reporting on the dissemination activities.

Introduction

The DISCOVER project will develop a comprehensive solution that includes:

- a) In-situ autonomous, synchronous, continuous and intelligent data acquisition and analysis;
- b) A BIM-based framework for the identification and measuring of components and materials in the existing built works;
- c) BIM-based demolition and recovery protocols to minimize cost and environmental impacts; and
- d) A secondary material database with emphasis on traceability and accessibility.

This framework will leverage state-of-the-art robotics, sensing and AI technologies with a comprehensive understanding of the potential of components from end-of-life built works.

This DC Plan lists all planned dissemination and communication activities, tools and channels, and matches them with main target groups and key performance indicators. This document will be a reference framework for evaluating the impact of dissemination activities and will be updated and adjusted during the project's lifetime.

This document addresses the essential components of a successful communication and dissemination strategy by:

- Incorporating goals into communication and dissemination activities;
- Defining and assigning to the partners the actions and requirements for the communication and dissemination process, as set in Article 17 — Communication, dissemination and visibility of Grant Agreement;
- Identifying primary target audiences;
- Presenting the key details of the project and showcasing the primary resources;
- Establishing the tools and communication channels that will be used to reach the target audience, along with the necessary actions and resources;
- Providing a timeline of dissemination activities that will take place throughout the project's duration;
- Outlining the internal monitoring, evaluation and reporting of dissemination activities;
- Providing the relevant instructions and templates to maximize the project's outcomes well after it has ended.

Communication and dissemination activities will be carried throughout the entire lifespan of the project (M1-M48), under the dedicated work packages (WP8, 9, 10 – Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication) in an effort to raise awareness on the project's activities and maximize its impact.

Before setting up the D&C Strategy, it is important to analyse Communication and Dissemination definitions, two core concepts that the current document and WP8 deal with.

- *Dissemination - means to make the results of a project public (by any appropriate means other than protecting or exploiting them, e.g. scientific publications).*
- *Communication on projects – a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i)*

the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

The purpose of the communication activities is to make the research activities known to multiple audiences (in a way that they can be understood by non-specialists) and the activities must address the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding, by considering aspects such as (i) transnational cooperation in a European consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed to achieve more than otherwise possible) or (ii) scientific excellence or (iii) contributing to competitiveness and to solving societal challenges.¹

1. Communication and Dissemination Objectives

The objectives of communication and dissemination serve as a catalyst to ensure that the project's outcomes - scientific results, robotic solutions, tools, AI algorithms, models, open dataset - are consequently disseminated to a broad spectrum of stakeholders in order to maximize the impact of those outcomes as well as to strengthen internal communication within the partnership and stakeholders.

The main objectives of communication and dissemination are to:

- Encourage involvement in the project's activities;
- Engage local, regional and European stakeholders through a series of relevant activities, events and conferences;
- Ensure that the key messages are communicated to its target audiences;
- Raise awareness among construction and deconstruction stakeholders;
- Disseminate the project's outcomes in an open, inclusive and transparent way;
- Foster synergies with other initiatives, capitalizing on existing dissemination channels and networks to ensure efficient communication and understanding.

To ensure lasting & far-reaching impact beyond the specific project goals and outcomes, the DISCOVER partners will implement DE&C activities embedded in a strategy based on four pillars (Figure 1):

Figure 1. The main pillars of the D&C activities.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>
www.discover-horizon.eu

DISCOVER Solutions - This pillar highlights the core outputs of the project:

- Autonomous robotic solutions for material sensing and identification;
- AI algorithms for recognition, quantification, and localization of construction elements;
- Open semantic BIM, an open dataset for deconstruction elements, and a digital catalogue with routes and output databases;
- A decision-making tool to guide sustainable deconstruction practices.

Demonstration - Aimed at showcasing the practical application of DISCOVER's innovations, this pillar includes:

- Training sessions to familiarize stakeholders with the project's tools and methodologies;
- Online MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) for wider learning and adoption;
- On-site demonstration events in Portugal, Belgium, Poland, and Spain, allowing stakeholders to experience the technology firsthand.

Exploitation – Focusing on ensuring the scientific and commercial uptake of project outcomes, this pillar includes:

- Publication of scientific papers to share results with the academic community;
- Clustering activities to foster collaboration and innovation with related projects and stakeholders;
- Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) activities to protect and promote the innovative solutions developed.

Actions and Networks - To expand the reach of the project and ensure engagement, this pillar targets:

- Existing professional networks and construction companies;
- Universities, public authorities, and the general public, aiming to influence industry practices and public policy.

2. Timeline of D&C Plan

The timeline for dissemination and communication activities in DISCOVER is structured into four main phases that span the project's duration (Figure 2). Each phase outlines essential activities in communication, dissemination, and exploitation to ensure the project's visibility and long-term impact. The D&C Plan is structured around three main pillars: (1) Communication, (2) Dissemination, and (3) Exploitation:

In Year 1, the focus is put on establishing the project's identity and online presence, initiating promotional activities, and developing the exploitation plan. Years 2-3 focus on deeper dissemination efforts, including pilot and site events, scientific publications, and the introduction of intellectual property rights (IPR) management. Year 4 is marked by a final dissemination event, continued presentations and publications, and exploitation activities that will extend after the finalization of the project to sustain impact.

Figure 2. D&C Timeline.

Detailed objectives for each period are presented in the following table (Table 1):

Period	Objectives	Communication and Dissemination tools to be used
1st Period M1 – M6	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Design the D&C strategy of DISCOVER 2. Design the logo and the visual identity of the project 3. Prepare the promotional package (leaflet, poster, templates, rollup - banner) 4. Set – up the project’s digital dissemination tools (social media accounts, website) 5. Announce the project widely 6. Design the exploitation plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project’s DC Plan - Project’s logo - Project’s website - Project’s social media accounts - Project’s poster, leaflet, banner, presentation and report template - Project’s press release - Project’s newsletter - Contact with other projects and networks
2nd Period M7- M24	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Widely disseminate and communicate the project’s concept and progress 2. Engage a wide variety of stakeholders 3. Establish synergies with several relevant projects 4. Present the project at national and international events 5. Design IPR management plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continued use of project’s DC Plan, logo, website, and social media - Updated promotional materials - Press release - Newsletter - Collaboration with related projects and networks - Participation in external events

Period	Objectives	Communication and Dissemination tools to be used
3rd Period M25 - M48	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promote the project’s findings and achievements at key industry and academic events. 2. Publish final research findings and insights in scientific journals 3. Maintain strong synergies with relevant project and cluster initiatives 4. Conduct the demo site events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continued use of DC Plan, logo, website, and social media - Promotional materials - Press release - Newsletter - Promotional videos - Collaboration with related projects and networks - Participation in external events
4th Period Beyond the end of the project	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dissemination of project results 2. Post – project exploitation of the project’s results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium partners’ networks and means of communications

Table 1. Dissemination & Communication Phases, Objectives, and Tools.

3. Target Groups

The main objective of the DC Plan is to support the DISCOVER Partnership in achieving its goals through structured and appropriate means and tools and to maximize the impact of the DISCOVER project and effectively engage with a diverse range of target groups. DISCOVER consortium has devised a multifaceted approach that considers the diverse nature of the different stakeholders. The first step to achieving this goal is to identify the main target groups.

The following main groups of stakeholders have been identified as the main project audience (Figure 3), interested in the project outputs, and, therefore, targeted by the consortium for dissemination and communication activities:

- Industrial community in the construction and demolition activities: workers, general contractors, deconstruction and demolition companies, designers, architects, engineers and developers;
- Professionals and researchers in the areas of civil and building engineering, circularity, robotics, signal processing, AI and social sciences;
- Public authorities, policy makers;
- Professional associations and networks;
- Universities and R&D centers;
- Citizens and the general public.

Figure 3. DISCOVER's target groups.

3.1. Gender Dimension

The Dissemination and Communication strategy of DISCOVER will integrate a strong gender dimension across all activities. DISCOVER will actively engage with gender issue by using non-sexist language and imagery and promoting attendance and employability of women within the scope of the project through activities such as surveys, research activities, demo site events, conferences, training sessions, etc. The consortium will be respectful of gender equality and ensure there is no discrimination on the basis of a person's gender during the project's activities.

4. Communication main channels and tools

The DISCOVER communication strategy will spread the project's vision to key stakeholders, main target groups and the public that can benefit from the results and outcomes of the project. The main communication channels and tools that will be utilized during the project are presented below (Table 2):

Communication Tools	
Project Logo and Graphical Identity	Logo
	Typeface, colours
	Digital Templates
Promotional Materials	Flyers, roll-up banners, posters
	Newsletters and press release
Online Communication and Social Media Channels	Project website
	Project social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter)
	Partners' Websites and Social Media publications

Table 2. DISCOVER's communication channels and tools.

4.1. Visual identity

A common branding was developed during the first months of the project to ensure the immediate recognition of the project. The logo, as the visual messenger of the project, will be used by all templates, reports, and dissemination activities throughout the project. The official DISCOVER logo (Figure 4) was selected to represent the project via an online poll by the majority of the voting partners. This design is adaptable to different screen and paper sizes, as well as different background colors, dark or light. The development of visual identity (Annex 1) provides consistent instructions on how the DISCOVER partnership should be visually represented in any situation.

Visual identity serves the following purposes in terms of communication:

- To direct partners in the partnership's communication. Partners must extensively inform their target audiences and national networks about the partnership and its activities. They, therefore, require guidelines to ensure effective external communication and to assist them in using communication materials;
- To maintain clarity and consistency across the various channels of communication, primarily events, digital (web, social media), and printed materials;
- To assist audiences (end users, stakeholders, etc.) in understanding the DISCOVER project, its objectives, and associated activities.

Figure 4. Alternative versions of the logo.

4.2. EU Visual identity

A particular attention must be addressed to the rules at the base of the EU visual identity elements. As a general rule, the program logo must be in proportion to the design to which it applies. Generally, it should be placed on the first page or equally prominent place. The DISCOVER logo and the EU emblem must be prominently displayed on all communication materials created for the project (such as presentations, deliverables, etc.).

EU emblem:

A clear space must be used for the disclaimer. Disclaimer:

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Both the EU emblem, together with the Disclaimer, and the visual identity rules of the European Commission may be found in the European Research Executive Agency online repository².

Apart from applying the logo on all dissemination materials that will be produced, the central creation of basic electronic templates is suggested to be used by all participating partners for all project communication:

- Development of a PPT template to be used for all presentations held during the project, e.g. in the framework of events, courses, and workshops (Annex 3). The template should have the project's logo, the EU logo, as well as a specified place to fill in the logo of the national partner. An effort should be made to include either the motto or a detail of the project's main creative visual in the template design;
- Development of a template for publications to be used for the deliverables of the project. Given that all partners have wide networks, the aim is to disseminate the outputs of the project beyond the countries of the partnership providing for a broader dissemination (Annex 4);
- Development of a press release template tailored for the general public will ensure effective communication and circulation in the media, both to disseminate project developments and results and stimulate awareness of homo- and transphobia (Annex 5).

4.3. Promotional materials

Dissemination and promotional materials, namely, poster, flyer and rollup banner (Annex 2) have already been designed. The main scope of these materials is to share information about the project with target groups and the broader audience in order to raise awareness and reassure a dissemination impact of the project, as well as effective connection with project activities, outcomes and results. The materials include the project logo, the reference to the European Commission with the EU, as well as reference/information on the following areas:

- The project objectives and scope
- The project partnership
- The project duration
- The main activities and key messages
- The expected outcomes/results
- The target groups addressed
- The innovative approach of the project
- The disclaimer
- The link to the project's website

² https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en
www.discover-horizon.eu

- Social media accounts

The materials will be used on multiple occasions, such as workshops, pilot demonstration events, national and international fairs or any other relevant event organized for the DISCOVER project addressing all target groups and key stakeholders involved. These materials will be updated at M36 to include the latest project outcomes, enhancing their value for use in events such as demo site events, scientific publication and presentation at regional, national and international events in order to achieve a wider impact on the DISCOVER results. Finally, these materials can be also integrated in their electronic format into mailings addressed to recipient groups of the mailing lists. The materials will be developed in English, and they will be available on the DISCOVER website.

4.4. DISCOVER Project website

The DISCOVER project website is the principal dissemination tool and information gateway, where all the project outputs and results will be uploaded (Figure 5). The content of the website is in English, which is the project working language. The official website address of the project is <https://discover-horizon.eu/>.

PEDMEDE is the Work Package Leader and in charge of the website development and operation. At the same time, all partners will have responsibility for evaluating and providing input for the uploaded content throughout the project lifetime. The content will be adapted throughout the project's lifetime, and the website will be maintained for four years after the completion of the project to support the exploitation of its results.

In general, the development of the website is aimed at:

- Providing feedback and information regarding the project objectives, scope, content, milestones and activities, target groups to be addressed, key stakeholders to be involved, as well as the involved partners and countries;
- Providing information regarding the project rationale, its impact, along with aligning with national and European priorities and needs;
- Providing free access to the project deliverables and results, as well as project reporting in the framework of its WPs;
- Providing news about the progress of project development;
- Providing links to social media networks;
- Providing contact information and networking among users. Supplementary key

features of the project website:

- User-friendly and highly interactive;
- Providing the opportunity for communication among the users, along with direct linking with social media;
- Being adaptable through suggestions coming directly from the end users and through the interaction among potential users to generate a critical mass of multipliers;

- Detailed statistical data on website visits, number of repeated visits, average visit duration and country of origin will be followed-up and reported.

Figure 5. Snapshot of the DISCOVER website.

The structure of the website allows for identification of the sections and subsections to be developed within the DISCOVER partnership framework. The main identified sections are:

- 1 – ABOUT DISCOVER
- 2 – DEMOS
- 3 – CONSORTIUM
- 4 – NEWS
- 5 – DELIVERABLES/PUBLICATIONS
- 6 – CONTACT

The baseline target for the project website has been set to 5.000 visits. Metrics and online tools will be used to monitor the website's activity. PEDMEDE will review these data every six months to assess progress, address potential risks, and ensure this KPI is achieved.

4.5. Social media accounts

The main goal of the DISCOVER's social media accounts is to broaden its audience by creating an online community made up of followers and supporters, and maximize the impact of the project's updates, news, and results. The project social media accounts will serve as complementary dissemination and communication channels in addition to the project website throughout the four-year duration of the project. These accounts will also be maintained after the completion of the project.

The DISCOVER project is presented on LinkedIn and X (former Twitter), as these channels are more relevant to scientific and industrial audience. Both channels will be regularly

updated with news on the project itself, as well as general news with relevance to the DISCOVER project.

The LinkedIn platform was selected to promote the project to a more professional audience. Partners are expected to support the project's LinkedIn profile, repost the posts via their accounts and invite followers. The DISCOVER LinkedIn account aims to reach at least 500 followers (Figure 6).

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/discover-horizon-project/>

Figure 6. Snapshot of DISCOVER's LinkedIn account

The project partners are expected to contribute to the project's X (previously Twitter) account on a regular basis by retweeting its content via their personal accounts and suggesting relevant content. The DISCOVER X account aims to reach at least 500 followers (Figure 7).

X: <https://x.com/Discover1017435>

Figure 7. Snapshot of DISCOVER's X account.

The use of hashtags allows the project's messages to reach wider audiences, and short and precise posts can actively engage a large pool of stakeholders. The list of hashtags below is currently being used on the DISCOVER social media channels on a regular basis. This list

reflects hashtags and keywords that will be used for targeted content to specific target audience. This common hashtag list must be used by all partners on their posts, to maximise the outreach (Table 3).

DISCOVER Hashtags
#HorizonEU
#DISCOVERProject
#ResearchImpactEU for posts related to research outcomes
#EUInnovation for posts about innovations or technological advances

Table 3. DISCOVER hashtag list.

PEDMEDE will manage and post updates on the project LinkedIn and X/Twitter channels. All project partners are expected to contribute by sending materials to PEDMEDE, including event participation and project-related outcomes available for sharing. PEDMEDE will develop at least two DISCOVER-related post per month to enhance the visibility of the project and increase the engagement of the relevant stakeholders.

Partners corporate social media include mainly Facebook, LinkedIn, X, and Instagram. Around 300 posts are expected to be published during the lifecycle of the project. The recommended frequency of the posts is one per month, following the project’s process.

Apart from the LinkedIn and X accounts functioning from the outset of the project, a YouTube channel dedicated to the DISCOVER project will be set up by PEDMEDE in the second year of the project for dissemination and communication of the project updates, outcomes and events.

Within the framework of the DC plan, four promotional videos will be created with the goal of attracting public attention to the project’s activities and promoting various aspects of the project. The video content will be created in collaboration with all partners.

The videos will be posted on the DISCOVER’s YouTube channel, the project’s website, as well as on the social media accounts of the project (X, LinkedIn). Furthermore, these videos will be disseminated through the partners’ social media accounts (X, LinkedIn).

PEDMEDE and UPC will be responsible for uploading the videos to the YouTube channel.

4.6. Newsletters

Newsletters comprise a tool that will facilitate the dissemination of up-to-date information within the project partnership and the partners’ networks. Subscribers will have direct access to project information, while its diffusion to wider audiences will allow for visibility, sharing and dissemination of engaging content of project activities. The foreseen development and publication of Newsletters include one (1) newsletter every six months. Total eight (8) newsletters through the whole lifecycle of the project.

The project’s newsletters will be downloadable through website, thus making directly available information concerning activities and results and supplying a constant update of the project’s progress to all beneficiaries and potential stakeholders. The newsletters will be

sent to the registered subscribers by a specific tool (e.g., mailchimp) at the national and international level on behalf of the DISCOVER partnership.

Although the content of each issue will be agreed upon by the partners, in general, each newsletter will indicatively include the following sections:

- An introductory section briefly describing the DISCOVER project;
- Progress updates/what has been implemented? (News of the project progress, project meetings, important milestones, etc.);
- What is currently happening/what is being implemented now? (Activities that were implemented recently or are still ongoing);
- A section dedicated to future developments/what is next? (Upcoming events, important activities, demo sites events, etc.);
- A section dedicated to the clustering initiatives (Presentation of relevant projects, news from other initiatives, etc.);
- News related to AI models, robotics, Construction and Demolition (C&D), Construction and Demolition Waste (C&DW).

4.7. Media releases

To ensure efficient communication and visibility in mainstream and specialised media of the project, press releases will be distributed as often as necessary considering project milestones. Partners will adapt them to their corporate language (if needed) and make them circulate throughout their own communication channels.

At least four (4) press releases are foreseen throughout the project. Each of them will aim at generating interest in the project's activities.

Each partner may issue its own press releases but must inform all partners, particularly PEDMEDE and UPC, in advance to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the information. Information will also be collected for reporting purposes to ensure that key stakeholder groups are effectively reached.

5. Dissemination channels and tools

A variety of dissemination channels and tools have been chosen from the proposal stage and will be prepared to facilitate the implementation of the activities by all partners to ensure the highest dissemination and exploitation impact. The DISCOVER consortium will publish research findings in reputable scientific journals and present the outputs at conferences, such as MEDER, ARK, ISRR, ICRA.

5.1. Events

The DISCOVER partners will actively participate in both international, regional, and local conferences, fairs and workshops to disseminate the project results and raise awareness about the DISCOVER activities and achievements. The DISCOVER Partnership will participate in and promote the results of the project into different events throughout the years. All partners will include an acknowledgment in project-related publications and

presentations, stating: “This work was supported by the Horizon Europe Programme [Grant Agreement number 101129909]”.

Throughout the duration of the DISCOVER, the partners will participate in external events with the aim of:

- Introducing and explaining the concept and innovative approach of the project;
- Staying updated with the latest advancements in the field;
- Sharing and distributing the knowledge and insights gathered throughout the DISCOVER;
- Building and strengthening connections with stakeholders;
- Disseminating the activities and outcomes of the project;
- Increasing overall awareness of the project and its impact.

Consortium partners will have access to the leaflet, poster, banner, slide template, and publications when they participate in external events to guarantee consistency and shared aesthetics of project presentations and communication channels. The project logo will be prominently displayed, and the same colors will be used in all of these communication and dissemination materials.

All partners are encouraged to present the DISCOVER project at external events to increase the impact of the project. The Coordinator must be informed in advance about the planned presentations and their content. When necessary, to ensure accuracy and consistency, the presentation content will be developed in cooperation with the Coordinator.

An indicative list of selected national and international fairs, conferences and key market events is presented in Table 4.

Event	Type	Year
Internacional congress (ISRR)	Conference	2025
Internacional congress (IDETC), USA	Conference	2026
Internacional congress (ICRA), Viena	Conference	2026
National conference “Construção 2026”	Conference	2026
National conference “Construção 2028”	Conference	2028
ICAICE 2024: International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Civil Engineering	Conference	2024
Bauma fair	Trade fair	Annual
Smart City Expo World Congress	Trade Fair	TBA
IWAGPR (International Workshop on Advanced Ground Penetrating Radar), Greece	Conference	2025
International Conference on Ground Penetrating Radar	Conference	2026
SASE Conference – Society for Advancement of Socio-Economics	Conference	2025

Table 4. Indicative list of events.

5.2. Scientific publications

The DISCOVER partners will publish the most relevant results and achievements in scientific literature, dedicated journals and magazines to increase the project's visibility across the EU and internationally. According to the DISCOVER dissemination strategy, at least twenty (20)

publications (open access) of the project progress in high impact journals, with > 30% of them with more than one of the project beneficiaries 100% open access articles published in journals. For peer-reviewed scientific publications, a “green open access” policy is envisioned, which will ensure open access to publications within at most 6 months. The scientific publications that will arise in the context of the DISCOVER will be open access under the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY). The publications will be immediate, without any embargo period, applying the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

A list of selected scientific journals³ is provided in Table 5.

Scientific journals
Journal of Building Engineering
International Journal of Robotics
IEEE Transactions on Robotics
Research Journal of Field Robotics
Journal of Resource Conservation and Recycling
Journal of Construction and Building Materials
Journal of Waste Management
Journal of Cleaner Production
Journal of Cleaner Materials
Journal of Automation in Construction
Journal of Building and Construction Materials
NDT & E International
Journal of Conservation & Recycling Advances
Automation in Construction
Smart cities
Automatización para la Industria ³
Construction Management and Economics
Embuild Magazine
Journal of Sociology of work
Journal of Sociology of innovation

Table 5. Indicative list of scientific journals.

5.3. Demo site events and MOOCS

Two key components of the DISCOVER project’s dissemination strategy are demo events and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). The demo events are planned to showcase the project’s real-world solutions, while the MOOCs will ensure the widespread, long-term dissemination of knowledge.

The demo site events play a pivotal role in disseminating the DISCOVER project’s outcomes by offering diverse, tangible, and educational representations of sustainable construction and demolition practices. These demo sites will allow stakeholders, policymakers, industry professionals, and the public to witness the project’s solutions in action. A detailed dissemination plan for the demo site events will be developed by PEDMEDE 6 months before the beginning of the events.

³ Open Access Journals
www.discover-horizon.eu

Throughout the events, separate dissemination materials will be produced. Specifically, the demo sites events will generate a range of promotional content, including photos, videos, and audio-visual material, which will be used for communication purposes for courses, training sessions, workshops, and seminars to educate future professionals and stakeholders about sustainable deconstruction practices. Additionally, the dissemination materials created during the events will be shared through the DISCOVER website and social media channels.

Four (4) demonstration events at real demolition buildings and infrastructures in which the DISCOVER will be showed from beginning to end to C&D stakeholders, public authorities and the general public (Table 6). The DISCOVER model will be tested in four relevant demolition sites in four EU countries (Spain, Portugal, Poland and Belgium), offering a complete range of building and infrastructure typologies and wide geographical coverage to demonstrate the replicability potential of the solution proposed. The pilot testing events will also be used for disseminating project results and contributing to the project’s impact by engaging local, regional and European stakeholders in this series of showcasing events.

Demo site events	Type of Building	Timeline	Responsible partner
Portugal	Traditional building	M27-M31	C5Lab
Belgium	Residential building	M34-M38	TRACIMAT vzw
Poland	Concrete infrastructure site	M39-M43	TREE
Spain	Industrial building	M43-M47	H-ZERO

Table 6. Demo site events.

Except from the demo sites events, the Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) are also crucial in terms of dissemination of the project as their main aim is to spread the knowledge and to guarantee the DISCOVER maximum impact on society through the participation of the main stakeholders, such as academics, students, on-site workers, contractors, designers, architects, engineers, etc.

A MOOC consisting of 10 chapters will be developed to ensure maximum societal impact for the DISCOVER project. The chapters will cover topics such as circularity in construction, material identification using robots (OLIWALL and POKEYE), BIM modelling, sustainable demolition strategies, Web3-based material traceability tools, material quality assessment for reuse, analysis of residential and industrial infrastructure demolition cases, and best practices for industry stakeholders.

5.4. DISCOVER Final dissemination event

The final dissemination conference will be organized between month 37 and month 48 of the project. The main aim of this activity is to bring together the direct and indirect target groups of DISCOVER and disseminate all the project’s outcomes and results as well as ensuring the long-term sustainability of the project’s impact beyond its completion. The content and organizational details of the final dissemination event will be discussed and determined in close collaboration with all the partners. PEDMEDE will lead this task.

6. Clustering Networks and Synergies

The establishment of synergies and the use of networks for the dissemination of the project's results is pivotal for its successful implementation. This need was identified during the proposal stage, leading to the establishment of dedicated tasks led by TECNALIA aimed at fostering collaborations, participating in, and promoting clustering initiatives (T8.4 and T9.3). These tasks focus on actively engaging with stakeholders and policymakers, creating clustering networks to enhance collaboration and raise awareness about sustainable end-of-life (EoL) waste management. By building on previous outcomes and introducing new advances and opportunities, the project will facilitate data sharing and integration from other relevant projects and initiatives (Table 7).

This approach aims to create a community that expand the project's impact by forming or joining clusters with associated projects, thereby enabling structured knowledge sharing and benchmarking of outcomes. This strategy not only broadens the reach of the project but also provides opportunities for feedback and evaluation of the impacts of reinforcement techniques for upskilling.

Acronym	Title	Description	Period	Contribution to DISCOVER
RecycleBIM	Integrated Planning and Recording Circularity of Construction Materials through Digital Modelling	The project intends to make a multi-national and multi-stakeholder effort towards the creation of an integrated framework for circularity of raw materials of construction, leveraged on the wealth of information that is brought about by 'Building Information Modelling'.	2022-2025	This project is creating an integrated framework for the circularity of construction raw materials, leveraging on the information brought about by 'BIM' fed from handheld laser scanning and manual inspection to allow semi-automated digital twins of buildings at a controlled cost which sets the ground to complete automation proposed by DISCOVER.
AI4WATER	Digital Twins for irrigated agriculture	This project aims at optimizing the use of the available hydric resources, mitigating the effects of the increasing water shortage in agriculture, and improving food security, by creating a Digital Twin (DT) of an	2021-2023	This project uses mobile robots, combined with GPR and ML for autonomously identifying and mapping the humidity of the subsoil. The goal is to feed a digital

Acronym	Title	Description	Period	Contribution to DISCOVER
		irrigation sector in the Urgell or Segarra-Garrigues (Lleida).		twin for optimizing irrigation resources. DISCOVER proposes to use GPR and robots in the construction sector. Robots, control and identification algorithms need to be adapted to the case.
ICEBERG	Innovative Circular Economy Based solutions demonstrating the Efficient recovery of valuable material Resources from the Generation of representative End-of-Life building materials	This project aims to develop and demonstrate novel cost-effective circular smart solutions for an upgraded recovery of secondary building raw materials along the entire circular value chain: from end-of-life building materials (EBM) to new building products prepared for circularity, resource-efficiency and containing 30wt% to 100wt% of high-purity (>92%) recycled content.	2020-2024	ICEBERG designs and validates advanced technologies for high-purity secondary raw materials through 6 European circular case studies, covering wood, concrete, mixed aggregate, plasterboard, glass, and insulation materials. The developed tools and results of the case studies on the CE of building materials will be very valuable for DISCOVER.
BAMB	Buildings As Material Banks	BAMB created ways to increase the value of building materials. Dynamically and flexibly designed buildings could be incorporated into a circular economy—where materials in buildings sustained their value. This led to waste reduction and the use of fewer virgin resources.	2015-2019	BAMB created ways to increase the value of building materials. Its methodological framework will inspire the development of a multi-cycle circularity assessment framework within DISCOVER.

Acronym	Title	Description	Period	Contribution to DISCOVER
CINDERELA	New Circular Economy Business Model for More Sustainable Urban Construction	The CINDERELA project aims to untap this potential by developing and demonstrating a new business model (CinderCEBM) to assist companies in setting up successful circular economy business cases based on waste-to-resource opportunities.	2018 -2022	DISCOVER will build upon the proposed online ICT platform for tracking and modelling the urban waste-to-product flows and learn from its production and marketing of SRM-based construction products supported by BIM.
CITYLOOPS	Closing the loop for urban material flows	The goal of CityLoops has been to support small and medium sized city administrations across Europe in promoting the transition to a circular economy, for two specific material streams: construction and demolition waste (CDW, including soil), and bio-waste - representing the two most significant material fractions in terms of environmental impact, overall volume, and economic significance. The project has demonstrated a variety of different approaches which local governments can take through a series of pilot actions within seven European cities.	2019 – 2023	CityLoops focus on closing the loops of urban construction and demolition (C&D) waste flow streams. The project can share knowledge, best practices, and case studies related to waste reduction, material reuse.
Mine. IO	Holistic Digital Mine 4.0 Ecosystem	The project focused on industrialization, informatization and sustainable development of the mining sector. We aim to provide solutions that will build a novel mining digital ecosystem and a	2023-2026	Holistic Digital Mine 4.0 Ecosystem is focused on industrialization, informatization and sustainable development of the mining sector. Mine.io solution will embrace the

Acronym	Title	Description	Period	Contribution to DISCOVER
		systemic structure for the implementation of Industry 4.0 in mining industrial environments. Mine.io solution will embrace the whole mining system value chain from resources' exploration, extraction, and processing to waste management and post mining activity.		whole mining system value chain from resources' exploration, extraction and processing to waste management and post mining activity. Web3 traceability developments will be explorer and replicated for building sector.

Table 7. Related EU-funded projects.

6.1. Roles and responsibilities

To ensure the achievement of the aims and objectives outlined in the DC plan, each consortium partner plays an essential role in dissemination and communication efforts. The involvement and contribution of every partner are essential to the effectiveness of communication tools and dissemination activities. Through content creation, event participation, and sharing results, partners will directly influence the project's development, including its activities, outcomes, and overall progress. Their engagement will maximize the project's visibility and ensure its impact is effectively communicated to the target groups.

Partners are required to help and support the project's online presence by providing useful and interesting material for social media and website posts, as well as promoting the posts to obtain more followers who will stay up-to-date on the DISCOVER's actions and outcomes.

Furthermore, partners are encouraged to support the project's wider promotion by attending relevant events/conferences, featuring the project on their professional websites and publishing in newspapers or professional magazines. More specifically, the contributions and actions expected from all partners are:

- To contribute relevant and updated content for the DISCOVER project website, social media accounts (LinkedIn, X), and the newsletter;
- To promote the website, SMAs and the newsletter through their professional networks;
- To present updates and outcomes of the DISCOVER project in conferences, fairs and other external events;
- To disseminate the promotional material of the project (flyer, poster);
- To develop scientific publications related to the outcomes of the DISCOVER project.

Regarding the demo site events, there are also specific roles and responsibilities as follows:

H-ZERO, as the lead partner for WP6 (which is dedicated to the demo site events), will collaborate with the other responsible partners — c5LAB, TRAC, and TREE — to define the strategic approach for each event. This will be done in consultation with CIT and PEDMEDE,

who are co-responsible for the communication and dissemination (C&D) aspects of the events.

The lead partners for the demo site events will be responsible for developing dissemination materials, such as pictures, videos and audio-visual materials during the events in order to increase the impact of these events and boost the engagement of the target groups as these events will be the legacy of sustainability in construction elements and materials reuse for the DISCOVER project.

CIT and PEDMEDE will provide guidance to the partners on the specific dissemination materials to be produced, ensuring consistency and quality. Additionally, PEDMEDE will be responsible for uploading the videos, articles, and other content related to the demo events to the DISCOVER website and social media platforms.

7. Monitoring and evaluation of CD activities

Throughout the project's life cycle, the dissemination and communication activities will be monitored to ensure alignment between planned actions and actual outcomes. PEDMEDE will lead the monitoring and evaluation of the DISCOVER's dissemination efforts, but the entire project consortium will need to collaborate closely, staying informed of their activities and results at all stages.

The table below summarizes the KPIs selected to measure the impact of the DISCOVER's D&C activities (Table 8). The metrics, the targets, and the needs will be adjusted to the project's results and will be included in the updated deliverable (M18).

KPI's	Metrics	Target
DISCOVER website	No. of visits	5,000
	Pages viewed	12,000
	Views/ Downloads of the project deliverables, publications and flyer	500
Social media accounts (LinkedIn, X)	No. of X followers	500
	No. of LinkedIn followers	500
Promotional materials (Flyer, Poster, Banner)	No. of design	2
National/international fairs, conferences and key market events	No. of attended events	>20
Newsletter	No. of newsletters	8
	No. of subscribers	300
Posts on partners' social media accounts	No. of posts on partners' accounts	>300
Media releases	No. of media releases	4
YouTube videos	No. of videos uploaded to the DISCOVER YouTube channel	4
Articles published on partners' websites	No. of articles	>20
Scientific publications	No. of publications	>20
DISCOVER Final Dissemination event	No. of conducted events	1

Table 8. DISCOVER's Key Performance Indicators.

7.1. Dissemination and Communication monitoring

To ensure the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication (D&C) activities, a monitoring and reporting process will be implemented throughout the project's life cycle. Each quarter, all partners will complete a Dissemination Reporting Template (Annex 7), where they summarize the main D&C activities they conducted. This template will allow regular, standardized documentation of D&C efforts by each partner. Additionally, partners are required to fill out Events, Scientific Publications, and Other Communications Templates (Annex 7). These templates are designed to capture all relevant dissemination activities, helping to track events effectively and ensure comprehensive reporting.

PEDMEDE will review the data periodically and incorporate key findings into Dissemination and Communication Report. This review process enables tracking of D&C efforts and early identification of any gaps or challenges, allowing different actions if needed. The monitoring documents and templates have been shared with all consortium partners, who are expected to report their D&C activities monthly. More specifically:

- **Dissemination reporting template** - This template will record all the dissemination and communication activities conducted by the partners. The document should be updated by all partners on a monthly basis. Keeping track of the activities will ensure that any problems or gaps will be observed early, and mitigation measures will be put in place in order to be solved.
- **Event reporting template** - This template should be filled by all partners whenever they organise or participate in an event (national and international events such as fair, workshop, conference, meeting etc.). Moreover, partners should inform PEDMEDE and UPC of their participation in upcoming events in advance to facilitate promotion via the website and social media channels.
- **Scientific publications** - This template should be filled out when the partners published in a paper in a scientific journal that relates to the findings and outcomes from Discover project. Keeping track of these publications is essential to meeting the DISCOVER's KPIs and enhancing the project's visibility and impact.
- **Other communication activities** - This template facilitates the identification of events (workshops, webinars) with topics relevant to the DISCOVER vision. Each partner should fill in this template and send the information to PEDMEDE for promotional purpose and to upload information to the DISCOVER website and social media accounts.

Conclusion

The Dissemination & Communication Plan (DC Plan) provides a detailed overview of the strategy and actions that will be implemented to promote the DISCOVER activities and their results in an efficient and impactful way. This plan aims to highlight all of the project's dissemination and communication activities necessary to ensure maximum impact of the project through various communication and dissemination channels and actions to engage with the identified target groups.

The plan will be updated to include results collected and to ensure it aligns with evolving goals and objectives of Discover in M18, M36, and M48.

Annexes

Annex 1. DISCOVER Corporate design and toolbox

LOGO PRESENTATION GUIDELINES

Color Palette

Green:

Symbolizes growth, harmony, and freshness. It can be used to highlight elements related to innovation and sustainability.

Blue: Conveys trust, stability, and intelligence. Use it as the primary color to establish a sense of reliability and professionalism.

WEB : 3EB462
RGB : R:62 G:180 B:98
CMYK : C:74% M:0% Y:86% K: 0%

WEB : 363A62
RGB : R:54 G:58 B:146
CMYK : C:96% M:96% Y:0% K: 0%

WEB : 5ABDE9
RGB : R:90 G:189 B:233
CMYK : C:59% M:7% Y:0% K: 0%

WEB : 179DC5
RGB : R:23 G:157 B:197
CMYK : C:78% M:21% Y:11% K: 0%

BACKGROUND COLOR

WEB : 12192B
RGB : R:18 G:25 B:43
CMYK : C:89% M:80% Y:52% K: 67%

DISCOVER

DISCOVER

Annex 2. DISCOVER Flyer, poster and rollup – banner

DISCOVER

The project

Digital, autonomous, Intelligent and Synchronous system for Continuous identification, Optimization and Value Extraction of Resources from the end-of-use built environment

Built Works ↔ **Material Banks**

AUTONOMOUS & CONTINUOUS IDENTIFICATION TOOLS

- › Robotic Solutions
- › Portable Invasive & Non-Invasive Sensors
- › Synchronous recognition

MARKETING & SOCIAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

- › Secondary Material Bank
- › Digital Reskilling Tools
- › Socio-Organizational Transformative Impact Analysis

INTELLIGENT & SYNCHRONOUS DIGITAL TWIN

- › AI-based Data Processing
- › Materials Digital Catalogue
- › Deconstruction Decision Making Tool

SUSTAINABLE & TRACEABLE PRODUCTS

- › Predemolition Protocols
- › Multicycle LCA & LCC
- › Web3-Based Traceability Tool

Follow us: Website:

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A comprehensive solution for circularity in the twin transition of the construction sector

Built Works ↔ Material Banks

This project has received funding from the European Union under the Marie Skłodé Curie Grant Agreement.

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Annex 3. PPT template

DISCOVER

Digital, autonomous, Intelligent and Synchronous system for Continuous identification, Optimization and Value Extraction of Resources from the end-of-use built environment

Title
Subtitle (if needed)
Event:
Date:
Author(s):

Funded by the European Union

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Annex 4. Template for deliverables

**Digital, autonomous, Intelligent and Synchronous system for
Continuous identification, Optimization and Value Extraction of
Resources from the end-of-use built environment**

DISCOVER

Title

WP Leader:

Submission date: xxx

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Annex 5. Template for press releases

DISCOVER

Digital, autonomous, Intelligent and Synchronous system for Continuous identification, Optimization and Value Extraction of Resources from the end-of-use built environment

Press Release

Date

For more information, please visit the [DISCOVER website](#) or contact:

Project Coordinator
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Spain
discover.project@upc.edu

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X

DISCOVER Consortium

The DISCOVER consortium comprises 14 partners from eight EU countries (Spain, the Netherlands, Portugal, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Poland, and France).

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Funded by the European Union

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Annex 6. Template for minutes of meeting

<p>DISCOVER</p>																		
<p>DISCOVER Grant Agreement N.101129909</p>																		
<p>MEETING MINUTES</p>																		
<p>WP/Task: Location: Date: Time:</p>																		
<p>Meeting Agenda _____ </p>																		
<p>Participants _____ 1. Name and surname – ORG 2. Name and surname – ORG</p>																		
<p>Minutes of Meeting _____</p>																		
<p>Tasks Summary and Action Items</p>																		
<table border="1"><thead><tr><th>Task</th><th>Due Date</th><th>Owner</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>1.</td><td>dd/mm/year</td><td>name, surname. ORG</td></tr><tr><td>2.</td><td></td><td></td></tr><tr><td>3.</td><td></td><td></td></tr><tr><td>4.</td><td></td><td></td></tr></tbody></table>				Task	Due Date	Owner	1.	dd/mm/year	name, surname. ORG	2.			3.			4.		
Task	Due Date	Owner																
1.	dd/mm/year	name, surname. ORG																
2.																		
3.																		
4.																		

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